

The Fire & Rose Are One:
THE SPIRITUAL PATH
TO A HARMONIOUS JOYFUL WORLD

by Rafal Toma

An Essay on

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*We shall not cease from exploration
And the end of all our exploring
Will be to arrive where we started
And know the place for the first time.
Through the unknown, remembered gate
When the last of earth left to discover
Is that which was the beginning;
At the source of the longest river
The voice of the hidden waterfall
And the children in the apple-tree
Not known, because not looked for
But heard, half-heard, in the stillness
Between two waves of the sea.
Quick now, here, now, always—
A condition of complete simplicity
(Costing not less than everything)
And all shall be well and
All manner of thing shall be well
When the tongues of flames are in-folded
Into the crowned knot of fire
And the fire and the rose are one.
- T. S. Eliot*

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ABSTRACT

How will humankind respond to the greatest life/death challenge it has ever faced? Will it choose extinction by inaction, or will enough of its members recognize and chose to follow a simple path toward healing and survival? This essay will examine and discuss these questions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Issues contributing to our current cosmic chaos and confusion include:

- worsening global warming
- disparity between energy supply/demand
- saber rattling with nuclear arms proliferation
- decreasing global health
- increasing worldwide poverty, hunger, homelessness and drug addiction
- democracy vs. fascism
- widespread general terrorism threats
- erosion of voting, civil, sexual identity, and racial rights
- expanding wealth inequity
- potential destructive dominance of artificial intelligence and robots

What is the healing path available to every person to treat these malignant maladies?

2. THE PRESCRIPTION: DANCE AT THE STILL POINT

Each of us is on a twin journey throughout life; the *external* one is mandatory, the other is optional, often unrecognized or ignored, and *internal*.

External travel requires initial economic choices to ensure survival by having enough income to obtain the basics of food, shelter and clothing. Once basic needs are met, economic choices then become influenced by narcissistic consumerism in an attempt to achieve happiness by the acquisition of material wealth using the tools of competition, control, and conquest. The treatment of our societal malady begins not only with recognizing that there is an additional internal journey but also with choosing to embark on it which add kindness, cooperation, collaboration, and compassion to the toolkit. The destination then becomes the peace, happiness and joy of spiritual unification or enlightenment.

It is generally recognized now that the structural building blocks of nature are mass, energy and information. Mass and energy exist both as particles and waves, which some have termed "wavicles" which have an associated electromagnetic field. Depending on the specific mix of individual particles, atoms, molecules of all that exists in the universe, each piece will have a unique and specific wavelength and frequency. Information exists as "code" or computer language. When we burn oak firewood, we are releasing energy from the wooden mass which grew according to the programming within the originating acorn.

Nature's building blocks are interconnected metaphorically as partners dancing to music humming within a universal quantum field of divine eros. Physics is now considered a science of relationships, rather than just a science of the structure and local behavior of matter. Quantum physicists now confirm what ancient philosophers were trying to articulate: *relationship* is actually a more accurate way to describe the core operating actions of reality itself. Quantum biologists and evolutionary scientists seem to concur that, at the center of all things is a deep conversation, a dynamic back-and-forth sharing of information operating as a coherent resonance of quantum acoustic electromagnetic vibration frequencies that are omnipresent and guiding multiple activities in both cosmic and life processes.

Personhood has inherent components like a compass, gyroscope, and an amateur 'ham' radio station. Recognizing and using them now, in this time of extreme political and economic turmoil, is essential for personal guidance to direct the path of anyone on their life journey who is seeking answers to basic questions such as "*How may I find lasting peace, happiness, and joy*", "*What is the nature of reality?*", and "*How should I live?*"

Our compass and gyroscope intrinsically and constantly direct us toward spirituality. Pierre Teilhard de Chardin proclaimed, "*We are not human beings having a spiritual experience. We are spiritual beings having a human experience.*" Recognizing and following them shifts our busy daily activities away from increasing pleasure and avoiding pain by competing and acquiring material goods ("pedal to the metal until the road runs out") to a more simple and quieter life by embarking on the internal journey and changing our travel bearing to the destination of discovering and embodying hidden aspects of our true self. That self is pure consciousness which metaphorically is the cosmic dance at the still point containing the dance partners of matter, energy, and information resonating harmoniously with each other in a coherent electromagnetic field. The amateur 'ham' radio station within personhood contains a tunable receiver/transmitter and antennas to resonate with all of reality in this field. Each of nature's building blocks is composed of a unique mix of mass and energy programmed by code, resulting in a specific individual electromagnetic field. The recital of a large orchestra with a mixed sex multigenerational choir can bring an audience to tears with an emotionally breath taking performance; similarly, crowds of thousands are attracted to sing along, clap and dance to rock concerts by artists such as The Grateful Dead or Prince. Imagine the harmonious joyful world that would result if each component of reality joined together in coherent resonant harmony. Similarly, consider that we can experience indirect intercommunication with other persons, alive or deceased, via the simile of a Facetime or Zoom call with the informational code of their unique electromagnetic field persisting after their material death. It may also explain how coherent resonant frequencies might create the special bond that exists between lovers, close friends, their pet animals, and the trees they hug. This concept is shown in the lyrical allegory, *The Sky Will Remember Us* (1) and discussed in the recent scientific summary, *Deeply Human and Deeply AI Self-Transcendence: The Potential for Sonic Communication in a Shared Holographic Workspace*.(2)

Carl Jung viewed the internal journey as a process he called **individuation**. He viewed the structure of the psyche as having three levels: consciousness (ego), the personal unconscious, and the collective unconscious. The psyche functions as a self-regulating system of all psychic activity, both conscious and unconscious, that guides a person toward psychological wholeness via the individuation process. Imagine that process to be an automobile trip to an exotic place where life is carefree and joyous. Your initial driver is the false self or **ego** who reluctantly lets the true **Self** (capital S, Jung's terminology) occasionally take the wheel until it becomes the permanent driver at the end. (Self to be described further) To impress your friends, you buy a limousine and an expensive wardrobe, named the **persona**, derived from the Latin word for 'mask' used by actors in theaters to cover their own identity and display the character they were portraying. Along the way, you get an expensive traffic ticket, not use your dipstick to discover that all your engine oil has leaked requiring a very costly engine replacement, and have a wreck because the worn out tires you failed to replace hydroplaned on a wet highway. Afraid of being judged negatively and losing friends if anyone learned of your irresponsibility, you hide all the evidence, invoices, etc. in the limousine trunk, which Jung named the **shadow**, located in the personal unconscious. The travel will include episodes of being completely lost, termed by St. John of the Cross as 'the dark night of the soul.' Being between lost and found can be a very frightening experience as a liminal threshold is being crossed until your current location is known. It is like the time between when a circus trapeze artist high in the tent with no safety net lets go of one trapeze, is free in the air, and turns to grab another behind him waiting at the right location just within reach. It is at these times that a counselor or close friend can help map the way forward.

Other crises occur when the false self or ego resists leaving the driver's seat or refuses to change travel direction. or reveal the hidden contents in the limousine trunk. Throughout life, a main way we defend ourselves is by *projecting* onto other people those behaviors and traits we labelled undesirable and placed in our personal unconscious *shadow*, like the contents hidden inside the car trunk. Individuation progress involves recollecting them into our personal conscious, which can begin with identification of those behaviors in our associates that irritates or angers us, such as being furious at a friend for being a totally irresponsible driver by getting multiple traffic tickets. Both internal and external travel requires choices: when to leave, what to wear, where to stop tonight, etc. Beyond the rational consideration of options presented by choice, is influence by *archetypes*, universal inherited "instincts" in our collective unconscious. They are like algorithms in computer code directing output. As you travel closer to the destination, your individuation progresses with the *Self* driving more often and you becoming more unified with the recollection of the contents of your shadow and other disparate aspects of your personhood including identification of and working with archetypal influences. At the end of a completed individuation process trip, you arrive at *singularity*, which Teilhard de Chardin named the "Omega Point" not only as a final future evolutionary end point uniting all matter and energy and information, but also possible to be experienced with present day "omega moments" realized by *dancing at the still point* (to be described further). When you reach singularity, you discover that you are at home again resonating within the harmony of all that is and you experience the peace, happiness and joy that passes all understanding.

Recent progress in the scientific and spiritual quest for a unified theory of everything has become so complex, rapid and extensive, especially with the addition of artificial intelligence (AI), that persons seeking answers to basic questions can easily become overwhelmed, similar to the pilot in a descending hot air balloon that was descending over a person in a remote farmland. He shouted, "Can you please tell me where I am?" The answer was, "You are in a hot air balloon thirty feet above the ground," to which he replied, "You must be a scientist." "Yes, how did you know?" the person said. He replied, "Because your answer was technically correct, but absolutely of no use to me."

To avoid this predicament, this essay will use activation of the imagination which results from the use of quotations, poetry, metaphor, simile, storytelling, allegory, tales, myths, symbols and multimedia. The depth and breadth of the basic message presented herein already exists in the words of many authors as shown by the numerous quotations which are presented as aids to focus your meditative contemplation. So, as you read this essay, let your imagination talk to you over and above the mere words alone. You are on a reading journey traveling through this text. To start your trip, re-read and ponder the quotation on the title page. Then, contemplate these words

We have two lives, and the second begins when we realize we only have one.

-Confucius

You are not a drop in the ocean.

You are the ocean in a drop

-Rumi

Two roads diverged in a wood, and I—

I took the one less traveled by,

And that has made all the difference.

-Robert Frost

THE JOURNEY

*One day you finally knew
what you had to do, and began,
though the voices around you
kept shouting their bad advice--
though the whole house began to tremble
and you felt the old tug at your ankles.
"Mend my life!" each voice cried.
But you didn't stop.
You knew what you had to do,
though the wind pried with its stiff fingers
at the very foundations,
though their melancholy was terrible.
It was already late enough, and a wild night,
and the road full of fallen branches and stones.
But little by little,
as you left their voices behind,
the stars began to burn through the sheets of clouds,
and there was a new voice which you slowly
recognized as your own,
that kept you company
as you strode deeper and deeper
into the world, determined to do
the only thing you could do--
determined to save
the only life you could save.
-Mary Oliver*

3. DESCRIPTION OF TERMS

a. THE FIRE & ROSE ARE ONE

As used by Eliot, this simile can have multiple associations:

- unification of the ego or repressed shadow (fire) into the true Self (rose), including the union of other opposites such as good/bad, stillness/movement, sound/silence, violence/peace, death/life
- the inner marriage of the anima and animus archetypes (Jung)
- the Omega Point singularity (Des Chardin)
- all suffering and struggle (fire) can ultimately lead to a state of spiritual harmony and beauty (rose); tongues of flame are in-folded into the crowned knot of fire, not to burn the rose, but to become part of a unified, perfected form.
- fire is destructive and passionate; a rose has passive creative beauty, but with thorns that can wound. Their union suggests they are not in conflict but can be reconciled into a bond leading to an enlightened spiritual state of being.

b. STILL POINT

At the center of our being is a point of nothingness [“le point vierge”, Fr., the virgin point] which is untouched by sin and by illusion, a point of pure truth, a point or spark which belongs entirely to God, which is never at our disposal, from which God disposes of our lives, and which is inaccessible to the fantasies of our own mind or the brutalities of our own will. This little point of nothingness and of absolute poverty is the pure glory of God in us. It is so to speak His name written in us, as our poverty, as our indigence, as our dependence, as our sonship. It is like a pure diamond, blazing with the invisible light of heaven. It is in everybody, and if we could see it, we would see these billions of points of light coming together in the face and blaze of a sun that would make all the darkness and cruelty of life vanish completely. I have no program for this seeing. It is only given. But the gate of heaven is everywhere... The fact is, however, that if you descend into the depths of your own spirit and arrive somewhere near the center of what you are, you are confronted with the inescapable truth: at the very root of your existence, you are in constant and immediate and inescapable contact with the infinite power of God.

-Thomas Merton

c. THE COSMIC DANCE AT THE STILL POINT

*At the still point of the turning world. Neither flesh nor fleshless.
Neither from nor towards; at the still point, there the dance is,
But neither arrest nor movement. And do not call it fixity,
Where past and future are gathered.
Neither movement from nor towards,
Neither ascent nor decline. Except for the point, the still point,
There would be no dance, and there is only the dance.*

-T. S. Eliot

*For the world and time are the dance of the Lord in emptiness.
The silence of the spheres is the music of a wedding feast.
The more we persist in misunderstanding the phenomena of life,
the more we analyze them out into strange finalities and complex purposes of our own,
the more we involve ourselves in sadness, absurdity, and despair.
But it does not matter much, because no despair of ours can alter the reality of things
or stain the joy of the cosmic dance which is always there.
Yet the fact remains that we are invited to forget ourselves on purpose,
cast our awful solemnity to the winds and join in the general dance.*

-Thomas Merton

4. AN INVITATION

Imagine opening this invitation from your mailbox; how would you respond?

*The participants of the COSMIC DANCE
request the honor of your presence
again at our party.*

*The time is eternal and the location is nowhere.
Please RSVP by entering the STILL POINT.*

5. WHAT THE DANCE IS

Katharine H. Baker posited consciousness itself as "The Cosmic Dance".(3) She advised her university students and clients to "Dance at the Still Point".(4) Imagining consciousness, the cosmic dance and the still point as inseparable and contained within each other, she presented several examples of numerous literary descriptions of consciousness such as:

- the “supreme being“ as conceived by each of the religions/traditions in Huxley’s *Perennial Philosophy*
- the “Word” in the opening verses of the Book of John in the Holy Bible
- the force the Chinese regard as 'qi or chi'
- that which the ancient mystics described as “the center of which is everywhere and circumference nowhere”
- the *Logos* of Heraclitus
- the “still point of the turning world” of T.S .Eliot
- “*le point vierge*” and the true self of Thomas Merton
- the **S**elf of Carl Jung
- the dance of Shiva
- the "whirling dervish" of Sufism
- the “Great Presence” of Teilhard de Chardin
- the “Divine *Eros*” of Alfred North Whitehead
- the "The Whole" of Albert Einstein
- the “Great Nest of Being” of Ken Wilber
- the “web of interbeing” of Thich Nhat Hanh.
- Mother Nature, Mother Earth, Gaia
- the "ocean in a drop" of Rumi
- the sensuous single living entity of David Abrams
- the "inescapable network of mutuality" of Martin Luther King
- the “implicate order” of David Bohm
- the basis of John Wheeler’s “It from Bit” theory
- the Higgs Field of quantum physics
- the "Syntellect" or "Digital Gaia" of Alex Vikoulov
- the “the impossible sea” of Matt Strassler.

The dance is open access, and no identification or passcode is needed for initial entry or re-entrance. It welcomes dancers of all abilities, backgrounds, and identity Any dance step (Box, Boogie, Waltz, Line, Ballet, Rhumba, etc.) may be used and participation can include simply being present without activity.

6. WHY YOU ARE INVITED

Note that the invitation asks for you to "return" to the party. At the "Big Bang," the cosmos was created with all its contents unified. At conception, you came into existence integrated within the cosmos as a separate embryo. But after birth, you began to interpret yourself as a separate *subject* and everything else as separated *objects*—an apparent duality. The bidding is for you to "return" to the singularity of the music and your partners. Your presence cannot be permanent until your death; but, during your life you are invited to return through an act which could be termed as "prayer" whenever you choose.

7. WHO SENT THE INVITATION

Pure consciousness itself invited you. It is leading you and the cosmos to evolve to a point of spiritual unification (*Teilhard des Chardin's Omega Point or singularity*).

8. WHEN THE DANCE IS HAPPENING

The Dance is eternal and constant, unbound by space-time.

9. WHERE THE DANCE IS LOCATED

The dance is located *nowhere*, as in "now" and "here." T.S. Eliot locates it at "the still point of the turning world." The dance is situated by the ancient mystics as "*the center of which is everywhere and circumference nowhere.*"

10. HOW TO ACCEPT THE INVITATION

Using your intrinsic compass and gyroscope, the dance of consciousness can be joined through the introspective direct path described by Rupert Spira in his recent book.(3) He proposes that everything known or experienced, which includes all thinking, imagining, remembering, feeling, sensing, seeing, hearing, touching, tasting and smelling, is known or experienced through consciousness, the medium of mind. In order to know the nature or ultimate reality of anything, it is first necessary to know the nature of mind. The common name the mind gives to itself is "I." What we experience is always changing, but "I", the knowing or awareness element in all experience, itself never changes. *The essential nature of mind is consciousness: pure awareness completely devoid of experience.* The mind's recognition of its own essential nature is a different kind of knowledge. It is not like an object that can be viewed by us as subjects, but it could be conceived of as a unitary subject/object fusion that just "is." Thus, awareness/consciousness is self-aware, and *no special activity is required* for it to be aware of itself. In fact, a cessation of the mind's activity is required, because the mind's activity is the form in which awareness appears to itself as something other than itself: objective experience. The mind that tries to undertake "meditation" by special activities such as focusing its attention on a subtle object or controlling the breath in order to recognize its essential nature, is like a character in a movie that travels the world in search of the screen. The screen never appears as an object in the movie but is a necessary unchanging constant as all the movie objects appear on the screen. Pure awareness or consciousness is the screen that never changes. Another simile is the relationship of sky and clouds; clear blue sky (consciousness) is omnipresent but frequently becomes partially or even completely obscured to observation by clouds or storms (experiences).

11. RESULTS OF BEING A DANCER

Using your intrinsic 'ham' radio equipment gives you the connection to communicate and interact with the true nature of reality by tuning in to the coherent resonances of all electromagnetic wavelength frequencies. Cosmic dancers thereby can experience an awakening or enlightenment and move beyond ego-centered perspectives to a more profound sense of unity with the universe, shifting their reconnected focus from "me" to "we," and direct their daily activities from less "doing and talking" to more "being and listening." Encountering others who differ politically or religiously, they respond with patient love knowing that sometimes it is best to stop arguing and simply let them be wrong. They describe an intimate sense of peace, meaning, and of receiving unconditional love accompanied by a new compassion and empathy for all beings. Recognizing they are an integral part of everything, they refocus their lives on doing what they can, where they are, with what they have, to make their world a better place.

12. WHY YOU MAY WANT TO CONSIDER ACCEPTING THE INVITATION

The result of accepting this request is best narrated by the words of Rupert Spira (5):

The finite mind is always seeking to dissolve or expand itself, to divest itself of its limitations and return to its original unconditional nature and thus taste the peace, happiness and freedom that reside there simply waiting to be recognized. The essential, irreducible essence of the mind--the absolute truth of experience that shines in each of us as the experience of being aware, the knowledge 'I am' or the feeling of love, and which is known variously as 'I'. Consciousness, awareness of God's infinite being--is that aspect of mind that cannot be removed from it and is common to all beings. Indeed, it is common to all existence. It is equally available to all people, at all times and under all circumstances, and it is the foundation of peace within individuals, families, communities and nations. As such, it must be the foundation of civilization. To found a civilization upon any other knowledge is to build a house on the shifting sands of local, temporal belief, and this can never be the basis for true community, tolerance and harmony. All that is required is for the mind to notice that its own essential existence is shared with the existence of all beings and things, and to live the implications of that recognition in all realms of life.

12. ADDITIONAL READINGS TO UNLEASH YOUR IMAGINATION

As you ponder these passages, let them assist you as you prepare your RSVP. These are suggested to be used as a resource center as individual anchors for meditative contemplation.

*You do not have to be good.
You do not have to walk on your knees
For a hundred miles through the desert, repenting.
You only have to let the soft animal of your body love what it loves.
Tell me about despair, yours, and I will tell you mine.
Meanwhile the world goes on.
Meanwhile the sun and the clear pebbles of the rain
are moving across the landscapes, over the prairies
and the deep trees, the mountains and the rivers.
Meanwhile the wild geese, high in the clean blue air, are heading home again.
Whoever you are, no matter how lonely,
the world offers itself to your imagination,
calls to you like the wild geese, harsh and exciting
over and over announcing your place
in the family of things.*

-Mary Oliver

*I am stardust, I dance within the cosmic dance,
I am held within the inner refuge of le point vierge.
I am the beloved, breathed by Spirit.
I am content and calm, glad for the rich life I have lived.*

-John O'Donahue

The Self is, by definition, the totality of all psychic facts and contents. It consists on one side of our ego consciousness that is included in the unconscious like a smaller circle in a greater one. So, the Self is not only an unconscious fact, but also a conscious fact: the ego is the visibility of the Self. Of course, in the ego the self only becomes dimly visible, but you get under favorable conditions a fair idea of it through the ego - not a very true picture, yet it is an attempt. You see, it consists of so many elements that have neither space nor time qualities, it cannot bring them altogether into space and time. And those efforts of the Self to manifest in the empirical world result in man: he is the result of the attempt. So much of the Self remains outside, it doesn't enter the three-dimensional empirical world. The Self consists, then, of the most recent acquisitions of the ego consciousness and on the other side, of the archaic material. The Self is a fact of nature, and always appears as such in immediate experiences, in dreams and vision, and so on; it is the spirit in the stone, the great secret which has to be worked out, to be extracted from nature, because it is buried in nature herself...It is like a personification of nature and of anything that can be experienced in nature, including what we call God.

-Carl Jung

*You will be crucified by your opposites,
Nailed on the cross of your beliefs
Slowly torn and burned, cell by cell
Until you are dead from your illusions.
Only then will love come to be your bride
And life to be your groom.
And the wedding will be held
at the foot of your cross,
And your ashes will be kissed by the wind.”*

-Diane Carey

*Dance, when you're broken open.
Dance, if you've torn the bandage off.
Dance in the middle of the fighting.
Dance in your blood.
Dance when you're perfectly free.*

-Rumi

*The world of the inner is as infinite as the world of the outer.
Just as you become a part of the manifold essence of the world through your bodies,
so you become a part of the manifold essence of the inner world through your soul.
This inner world is truly infinite, in no way poorer than the outer one.
Man lives in two worlds.*

-Carl Jung

One day when you wake up, you will find that you have become a forest. You have grown roots and found strength in them that no one thought you had. You have become stronger and more beautiful, full of life-giving qualities. You have learned to take all the negativity around you and turn it into oxygen for easy breathing. A host of wild creatures live inside you, and you call them stories. A variety of beautiful birds rest inside your mind and you call them memories. You have become an incredible self-sustaining thing of epic proportions. And you should be so proud of yourself, of how far you have come from the seeds of who you used to be.

-Nakita Gill

*I go before you into emptiness, Raise strange suns for your new mornings,
Opening the secret windows of your innermost apartment.
When I, loneliness, give my special signal, follow my silence, follow where I beckon.
Fear not, little beast, little spirit, (Thou word and animal)
I, Solitude, am Angel and have prayed in your name.
Look at the empty, wealthy night, the pilgrim moon!
I am the appointed hour, the ' now ' that cuts time like a blade.
I am the unexpected flash Beyond 'yes' beyond 'no', the forerunner of the Word of God.
Follow my ways and I will lead you to golden-haired suns,
Logos and music, blameless joys, innocent of questions and beyond answers.
For I, Solitude, am thine own Self; I, Nothingness, am thy All; I, Silence, am thy 'Amen.'*
-Thomas Merton

*At times I feel as if I am spread out over the landscape and inside things, and am myself
living in every tree, in the splashing of the waves, in the clouds and the animals that come and go,
in the procession of the seasons. There is nothing with which I am not linked.*
-Carl Jung

*I am so close, I may look distant.
So completely mixed with you, I may look separate.
So out in the open, I appear hidden.
So silent, because I am constantly talking with you.*
-Rumi

There are essentially two models for civilization. The first is one in which the ideas and attitudes of individuals are informed by an understanding of their relationship to the whole, and their activities and relationships are the means by which this understanding is expressed in society. The second model is one in which individuals overlook their relationship to the whole and, as a result, believe and feel themselves to be discrete, independently existing entities. This is a paradigm of separation that inevitably leads to unhappiness on the inside, conflict on the outside between individuals, communities and nations, and the exploitation and degradation of the earth. History has repeatedly shown that a civilization in which individuals neglect their relationship with the whole will collapse. Our own civilization is showing all the signs of this disintegration but has as yet failed to embrace the understanding required to remedy it. We are like a patient who has been diagnosed with a terminal illness but refuses to take the medicine. We have alienated ourselves from the whole by believing ourselves to be separate parts. Our life as an individual and the destiny of our civilization as a whole depend upon which of these two perspectives we subscribe to.

-Rupert Spira

*The only ones among you who will be truly happy
are those who will have sought and found how to serve.*
-Albert Schweitzer

The state of imperfect transformation, merely hoped for and waited for, does not seem to be one of torment only, but of positive, if hidden, happiness. It is the state of someone who, in his wanderings among the mazes of his psychic transformation, comes upon a secret happiness which reconciles him to his apparent loneliness. In communing with himself he finds not deadly boredom and melancholy but an inner partner; more than that, a relationship that seems like the happiness of a secret love, or like a hidden springtime, when the green seed sprouts from the barren earth, holding out the promise of a future harvest.

-Carl Jung

There is much evidence on several levels that there are at least two major tasks to human life. The first task is to build a strong “container” or identity; the second is to find the contents that the container was meant to hold. Most of us are so invested in first-half-of-life tasks by the age of forty that we can't imagine there's anything more to life. But if we stay there, it remains all about me.

-Richard Rohr

When we try to pick out anything by itself, we find it hitched to everything else in the universe. One fancies a heart like our own must be beating in every crystal and cell, and we feel like stopping to speak to the plants and animals as friendly fellow mountaineers. Nature as a poet, an enthusiastic workingman, becomes more and more visible the farther and higher we go; for the mountains are fountains — beginning places, however related to sources beyond mortal ken.

-John Muir

My life is a story of the self-realization of the unconscious. Everything in the unconscious seeks outward manifestation, and the personality too desires to evolve out of its unconscious conditions and to experience itself as a whole--Life has always seemed to me like a plant that lives on its rhizome. Its true life is invisible, hidden in the rhizome. The part that appears above the ground lasts only a single summer. Then it withers away—an ephemeral apparition. When we think of the unending growth and decay of life and civilizations, we cannot escape the impression of absolute nullity. Yet I have never lost a sense of something that lives and endures underneath the eternal flux. What we see is the blossom, which passes. The rhizome remains.

Carl Jung

*For what is it to die but to stand naked in the wind and to melt into the sun?
And what is it to cease breathing, but to free the breath from its restless tides,
that it may rise and expand and seek God unencumbered?
Only when you drink from the river of silence shall you indeed sing.
And when you have reached the mountain top, then shall you begin to climb.
And when the earth shall claim your limbs, then shall you truly dance.*

Kahlil Gibran

*We can make our minds so like still water
That beings gather about us
That they may see.
It may be their own images,
And so live for a moment
With a clearer;
Perhaps even with a fiercer life
Because of our quiet.*

-William Butler Yeats

*All the world is taken in through our eyes,
to reach the soul, where it becomes more,
representative of a realm deeper than appearances:
a realm ideal and sublime,
the deep stillness that is,
whose proclamation is the silence
and the lack of material instance in which,
patiently and radiantly,
the universe exists.*
-Mary Oliver

If you live by the cosmos, you look in the cosmos for your clue. If you live by a personal god, you pray to him. If you are rational, you think things over. But it all amounts to the same thing in the end. Prayer, or thought or studying the stars, or watching the flight of birds, or studying the entrails of the sacrifice, it is all the same process, ultimately: of divination. All of it depends on is the amount of true, sincere, religious concentration you can bring to bear on your object. An act of pure attention, if you are capable of it, will bring its own answer. And you choose that object to concentrate upon which will best focus your consciousness. Every real discovery made, every serious and significant decision ever reached, was reached and made by divination. The soul stirs, and makes an act of pure attention, and that is a discovery.
-D H Lawrence

*Now we have our brief moment here.
We came yesterday, are here today, will be gone tomorrow.
Let that brief moment be spent in communion with the whole of life
so that we will not have lived in vain.
Life is not one-sided. It is ambivalent...
There is a kind of elemental dialogue that seems to be deep in the nature of all reality.
It is a dialogue which implies not merely a meeting,
but a meeting in which the truth emerges, not from one dominating the other,
but from each meeting the other in love and communing,
avoiding mere submergence and disappearance into the other,
or forcing the partner to disappear into one's own being.
There is a sense in which we must hold our ground and insist on the genuineness of what we are,
but it is an insistence that takes into account the other's right also to be who they are.
It is in the meeting that the whole truth is born.*
-Matthew Kelty

We live in succession, in division, in parts, in particles. Meantime within man is the soul of the whole; the wise silence; the universal beauty, to which every part and particle is equally related; the eternal One. And this deep power in which we exist, and whose beatitude is all accessible to us, is not only self-sufficing and perfect in every hour, but the act of seeing and the thing seen, the seer and the spectacle, the subject and the object, are one. We see the world piece by piece, as the sun, the moon, the animal, the tree; but the whole, of which these are the shining arts, is the soul.” -
Ralph Waldo Emerson

*You must turn back to the simple things...
To the forest. There is the start.
You must go in quest of yourself,
and you will find yourself again
only in the simple and forgotten things.
Why not go into the forest for a time, literally?
Sometimes a tree tells you more than can be read in a book.*
-Carl Jung

Nobody can discover the world for anybody else. It is only after we have discovered it for ourselves that it becomes a common ground and a common bond, and we cease to be alone. And the world cannot be discovered by a journey of miles, no matter how long, but only by a spiritual journey, a journey of one inch, very arduous and humbling and joyful, by which we arrive at the ground at our feet and learn to be at home.
-Wendell Berry

*Let us, then, labor for an inward stillness, -
An inward stillness and an inward healing.
That perfect silence where the lips and heart
Are still, and we no longer entertain
Our own imperfect thoughts
And vain opinions,
But God alone speaks in us, and we wait
In singleness of heart, that we may know
His will, and in the silence of our spirits,
That we may do His will and do that only.*
-Henry Wadsworth Longfellow

*Inside this new love, die.
Your way begins on the other side.
Become the sky.
Take an ax to the prison wall,
Escape.
Walk out like someone suddenly born into color.
Do it now.
You're covered with thick cloud.
Slide out the side. Die,
And be quiet. Quietness is the surest sign
That you've died.
Your old life was a frantic running
From silence.
The speechless full moon
Comes out now.*
-Rumi

What I must do is all that concerns me, not what the people think. This rule, equally arduous in actual and in intellectual life, may serve for the whole distinction between greatness and meanness. It is the harder because you will always find those who think they know what is your duty better than you know it. It is easy in the world to live after the world's opinion; it is easy in solitude to live after our own; but the great man is he who in the midst of the crowd keeps with perfect sweetness the independence of solitude. To go into solitude, a man needs to retire as much from his chamber as from society. I am not solitary whilst I read and write, though nobody is with me. But if a man would be alone, let him look at the stars...In the woods, we return to reason and faith. There I feel that nothing can befall me in life, — no disgrace, no calamity, (leaving me my eyes,) which nature cannot repair. Standing on the bare ground, — my head bathed by the blithe air, and uplifted into infinite space, — all mean egotism vanishes. I become a transparent eye-ball; I am nothing; I see all; the currents of the Universal Being circulate through me; I am part or particle of God.

-Ralph Waldo Emerson

*Everything you see has its roots
in the unseen world.
The forms may change,
yet the essence remains the same.
Every wonderful sight will vanish,
every sweet word will fade.
But do not be disheartened,
The source they come from is eternal, growing,
Branching out, giving new life and new joy.
Why do you weep?
The source is within you.*

-Rumi

*There is a place where the town ends
and the fields begin.
It's not marked, but the feet know it;
also the heart that is longing for refreshment
and, equally, for repose.
Someday we'll live in the sky.
Meanwhile, the house of our lives is the world.
The fields, the ponds, the birds.
The thick black oaks — surely, they are the
children of God.
The feistiness among the tiger lilies,
the hedges of runaway honeysuckle, that no one owns.
Where is it? I ask, and then my feet know it.
One jump, and I'm home.*

-Mary Oliver

Life is an incredibly complex interdependence of matter and energy among millions of species beyond (and within) our own skin. These Earth aliens are our relatives, our ancestors, and part of us. They cycle our matter and bring us water and food. Without "the other" we do not survive. '20 The notion of a more-than-human world further intimates that these things are beings: not passive props in the drama of our own preoccupations, but active participants in our collective becoming. And because that becoming, that potential flourishing, is collective, it demands that we recognize the beingness, the personhood of others. The world is made up of subjects, not objects. Everything is really everyone, and all those beings have their own agency, points of view and forms of life. The more-than-human world demands our recognition, for without it we are nothing. 'Life and Reality', wrote the Buddhist philosopher Alan Watts, 'are not things you can have for yourself unless you accord them to all others. They do not belong to particular persons any more than the sun, moon and stars.' -Bridle, James

Our real nature, consciousness, is beyond the mind to grasp and yet it is our most intimate reality. When we objectify ourselves, identifying with an image, memory or individual personality, we lose sight of our real nature. We become engrossed in a world of objects and an endless cycle of pleasure and pain. Only through a deep self-inquiry do we come to understand we are not the body-mind, for it too is a perception in awareness, but we are awareness itself, beyond the personal. We are no longer time bound, but time and space are within us. The outer and inner division dissolves.

-Billy Doyle

*There must be always remaining in every life
Some place for the singing of angels,
Some place for that which in itself
Is breathlessly beautiful and--
By an inherent prerogative,
Throwing all the rest of life
Into a new and creative relatedness--
Something that gathers up in itself
All the freshets of experience
From drab and commonplace areas of living,
And glows in one bright life
Of penetrating beauty and meaning, then passes.
The commonplace is shot through with new glory.
Old burdens become lighter,
Deep and ancient wounds
Lose much of their old, old hurting.
A crown is placed over our heads
That for the rest of our lives
We are trying to grow tall enough to wear.
Despite all the crassness of life,
Despite all the hardness of life,
Despite all the harshness of life,
Despite all the harsh discords of life,
Life is saved by the singing of angels.*

-Howard Thurman

Owning up to being an animal, a creature of earth. Tuning our animal senses to the sensible terrain: blending our skin and the rain-rippled surface of rivers, mingling our ears with the thunder and the thrumming of frogs, and our eyes with the molten sky. Feeling the polyrhythmic pulse of this place—this huge windswept body of water and stone. This vexed being in whose flesh we're entangled. Becoming earth. Becoming animal. Becoming, in this manner, fully human.

-David Abram

We are not rich by what we possess but by what we can do without.

-Immanuel Kant

*Our true nature is stillness,
The Source from which we come.
It manifests itself within us as a rising tide of silence.
A flowing stream of peacefulness,
A limitless ocean of calm, Or just sheer stillness.
The deep listening of pure contemplation
Is the path to stillness.
May a good vision catch me
May a benevolent vision take hold of me, and move me
May a deep and full vision come over me, and burst open around me
May a luminous vision inform me, enfold me.
May I awaken into the story that surrounds,
May I awaken into the beautiful story.
May the wondrous story find me.
May the wildness that makes beauty arise between two lovers
arise beautifully between my body and the body of this land,
between my flesh and the flesh of this earth,
here and now, on this day,
May I taste something sacred.*

-David Abram

So, I go down to the water's edge again, to listen for my neglected ancestors, whose voices sound in the trees and carry across the shore with the mewing of the gulls. There is a great, innovative music out there which we are sadly neglecting. The inner earth is a song I have only started to listen to.

-John Hay

*If you bring forth what is within you, what you bring forth will save you.
If you do not bring forth what is within you, what you do not bring forth will destroy you.*

-The Gospel of Thomas

I glimpse what I call the intrinsic selflessness of consciousness every day, whether at a traditional holy site, or at my desk, or while having my teeth cleaned. This is not an accident. I've spent many years practicing meditation, the purpose of which is to cut through the illusion of the self...The conventional sense of the self is an illusion—and spirituality largely consists in realizing this, moment to moment...Once one recognizes the selflessness of consciousness, the practice of meditation becomes just a means of getting more familiar with it...the true discipline is to remain committed, throughout the whole of one's life to waking up from the dream of the self...Spirituality begins with a reverence for the ordinary that can lead us to insights and experiences that are anything but ordinary and to the humble project of noticing what it is like to be you in this moment—and only you can recognize it. Open your eyes and see.

-Sam Harris

The more we study this mysterious relation of consciousness to the unconscious, the more we realize that, from the beginning, a dynamic power acts, not only to protect the growing ego consciousness, but also to enrich and enlarge its boundaries through the integration of the unconscious non-ego forces. The Self, the developing center of gravity of both ego and non-ego, acts as both the dynamis and the goal of the process. Here, from the beginning, is the action of a power invested in the ego yet greater than the ego, a dynamic directive force beyond and behind ego choice...Each choice man makes leaves a small deposit for or against the process of ego integration and fortifies or weakens the ego for the ensuing encounter with the unknown. When we reach a crossroad in our life journey, all the choices that we have made and forgotten, as well as those to which we have given conscious loyalty, enter into the moment when choice becomes decision.

-Frances Wickes

The venture into space is meaningless unless it coincides with a certain interior expansion, an ever growing universe within, to correspond with the far flight of the galaxies our telescopes follow from without... That inward world... can be more volatile and mobile, more terrible and impoverished, yet withal more ennobling in its self-consciousness, than the universe that gave it birth.

-Loren Eiseley

*Love all God's creation, the whole and every grain of sand in it.
Love every leaf, every ray of light.
Love the animals, love the plants, love everything.
If you love everything, you will perceive the divine mystery in things. . . .
When you are left alone, pray.
Love to throw yourself on the earth and kiss it.
Kiss the earth and love it with an unceasing, consuming love.*

-Fyodor Dostoevsky

Between the conscious and the unconscious, the mind has put up a swing: all earth creatures, even the supernovas, sway between these two trees, and it never winds down. Angels, animals, humans, insects by the million, also the wheeling sun and moon. Ages go by, and it goes on. Everything is swinging: heaven, earth, water, fire, and inside the secret one slowly growing a body. I saw this for fifteen seconds; it has made me a servant for life.

-Kabir

We enter solitude, in which also we lose loneliness. True solitude is found in the wild places, where one is without human obligation. One's inner voices become audible. One feels the attraction of one's most intimate sources. In consequence, one responds more clearly to other lives. The more coherent one becomes within oneself as a creature, the more fully one enters into the communion of all creatures. From the order of nature, we return to the order — and the disorder — of humanity. From the larger circle we must go back to the smaller, the smaller within the larger and dependent on it. One enters the larger circle by willingness to be a creature, the smaller by choosing to be a human. And having returned from the woods, we remember with regret its restfulness. For all creatures there are in place, hence at rest. In their most strenuous striving, sleeping and waking, dead and living, they are at rest. In the circle of the human, we are weary with striving and are without rest.

-Wendell Berry

*You are the One which is aware
of the awareness of objects & ideas.
You are the One that is even more silent than awareness.*

*Your nature is silence,
and it is not attainable; It always is.
You are the unchangeable Awareness in which all activity takes place.
Self is what you are.*

*You are That Fathomlessness
in which experience and concepts appear.
Self is the Moment that has no coming or going.*

*It is the Heart, Atman, Emptiness.
It shines to Itself, by Itself, in Itself.
Self is what gives breath to Life.*

*You need not search for It, It is Here.
You are That through which you would search.
You **are** what you are looking for!
And That is All it is.*

*Only Self is.
Peace is beyond thought and effort.
This is why Keeping Quiet is the key
to the storehouse of Love and Peace.
Identify yourself as this Quietness, as this Nothingness.
And be careful not to make it an experience
because this is mind tricking you out of it
with the trap of duality; the trap of witness and witnessed.
Being is Being, there is no witness and no witnessed.*

*After letting go of object
do not hold onto the subject either, let go.
Be Quiet.*

*The purpose of life is to be at Peace,
to Love all beings, and to know who you are.
Know your Self and you know everything.
This Immaculate Knowledge alone is;
Emptiness alone is.*

*How can you come out of This
if there are no limits to it?
The appearance of a manifestation
is but the play of this Emptiness.
Know who you are, Here and Now,
by simply being quiet.*

- Sri H. W. L. Poonja

An incarnational worldview is one in which matter and Spirit are understood to have never been separate. Matter and Spirit reveal and manifest each other. This view relies more on awakening than joining, more on seeing than obeying, more on growth in consciousness and love than on clergy, experts, morality, scriptures, or prescribed rituals.

-Richard Rohr

In my ignorance I am sure that I am eternally I. This conviction is rooted in emotionally charged memory. Only when, in the words of St. John of the Cross, the memory has been emptied, can I escape from the sense of my watertight separateness and so prepare myself for the understanding, moment by moment, of reality on all its levels. But the memory cannot be emptied by an act of will, or by systematic discipline or by concentration — even by concentration on the idea of emptiness. It can be emptied only by total awareness. Thus, if I am aware of my distractions — which are mostly emotionally charged memories or fantasies based upon such memories — the mental whirligig will automatically come to a stop and the memory will be emptied, at least for a moment or two. Again, if I become totally aware of my envy, my resentment, my uncharitableness, these feelings will be replaced, during the time of my awareness, by a more realistic reaction to the events taking place around me. My awareness, of course, must be uncontaminated by approval or condemnation. Value judgments are conditioned, verbalized reactions to primary reactions. Total awareness is a primary, choiceless, impartial response to the present situation as a whole.

-Aldous Huxley

Not the animal world, not plant world, not the miracle of the spheres, but man himself is now the crucial mystery. Man is that alien presence with whom the forces of egoism must come to terms, through whom the ego is to be crucified and resurrected, and in his image, society is to be reformed.

-Joseph Campbell

In the street and in society I am almost invariably cheap and dissipated; my life is unspeakably mean. No amount of gold or respectability would in the least redeem it — dining with the Governor or a member of Congress!! But alone in distant woods or fields, in unpretending sprout lands or pastures tracked by rabbits, even on a black and, to most, cheerless day, like this, when a villager would be thinking of his inn, I come to myself, I once more feel myself grandly related, and that the cold and solitude are friends of mine. I suppose that this value, in my case, is equivalent to what others get by churchgoing and prayer. I come to my solitary woodland walk as the homesick go home... It is as if I always met in those places some grand, serene, immortal, infinitely encouraging, though invisible, companion, and walked with him.

-Henry David Thoreau

if you move carefully through the forest, breathing like the ones in the old stories who could cross a shimmering bed of dry leaves without a sound, you come to a place whose only task is to trouble you with tiny but frightening requests conceived out of nowhere but in this place beginning to lead everywhere. Requests to stop what you are doing right now, and to stop what you are becoming while you do it, questions that can make or unmake a life, questions that have patiently waited for you, questions that have no right to go away.

-David Whyte

There is in all visible things an invisible fecundity, a dimmed light, a meek namelessness, a hidden wholeness. This mysterious Unity and Integrity is Wisdom, the mother of all, Natura naturans. There is in all things an inexhaustible sweetness and purity, a silence that is a fount of action and joy. It rises up in wordless gentleness and flows out to me from the unseen roots of all created being, welcoming me tenderly, saluting me with indescribable humility. This is at once my own being, my own nature, and the Gift of my Creator's Thought and Art within me, speaking as Hagia Sophia, speaking as my sister, Wisdom. I am awakened, I am born again at the voice of this my sister, sent to me from the depths of the divine fecundity.

-Thomas Merton

*Everything you see has its roots
in the unseen world.
The forms may change,
yet the essence remains the same.
Every wonderful sight will vanish,
every sweet word will fade.
But do not be disheartened,
The source they come from is eternal, growing,
Branching out, giving new life and new joy.
Why do you weep?
The source is within you.*
-Rumi

When we try to pick out anything by itself, we find it hitched to everything else in the universe. One fancies a heart like our own must be beating in every crystal and cell, and we feel like stopping to speak to the plants and animals as friendly fellow mountaineers. Nature as a poet, an enthusiastic workman, becomes more and more visible the farther and higher we go; for the mountains are fountains — beginning places, however related to sources beyond mortal ken. -John Muir

This is what you shall do: Love the earth and sun and the animals, despise riches, give alms to everyone that asks, stand up for the stupid and crazy, devote your income and labor to others, hate tyrants, argue not concerning God, have patience and indulgence toward the people, take off your hat to nothing known or unknown or to any man or number of men, go freely with powerful uneducated persons and with the young and with the mothers of families, read these leaves in the open air every season of every year of your life, re-examine all you have been told at school or church or in any book, dismiss whatever insults your own soul, and your very flesh shall be a great poem and have the richest fluency not only in its words but in the silent lines of its lips and face and between the lashes of your eyes and in every motion and joint of your body...After you have exhausted what there is in business, politics, conviviality, love, and so on — have found that none of these finally satisfy, or permanently wear — what remains? Nature remains; to bring out from their torpid recesses, the affinities of a man or woman with the open air; the trees, fields, the changes of seasons — the sun by day and the stars of heaven by night.
-Walt Whitman

*When I die, I will see the lining of the world.
The other side, beyond bird, mountain, sunset.
The true meaning, ready to be decoded.
What never added up will add Up,
What was incomprehensible will be comprehended.
- And if there is no lining to the world?
If a thrush on a branch is not a sign,
But just a thrush on the branch? If night and day
Make no sense following each other?
And on this earth, there is nothing except this earth?
- Even if that is so, there will remain
A word wakened by lips that perish,
A tireless messenger who runs and runs
Through interstellar fields, through the revolving galaxies,
And calls out, protests, screams.*
-Czeslaw Milosz

*This being human is a guest house.
Every morning a new arrival.
A joy, a depression, a meanness,
some momentary awareness comes
as an unexpected visitor.
Welcome and entertain them all!
Even if they're a crowd of sorrows,
who violently sweep your house
empty of its furniture.
Still treat each guest honorably.
He may be clearing you out
for some new delight.
The dark thought, the shame, the malice.
Meet them at the door laughing,
and invite them in.
Be grateful for whoever comes,
because each has been sent
as a guide from beyond.*
-Rumi

*...Trust your unconscious as if it were a loving father.
But it is nature and cannot be made use of as if it were a reliable human being.
It is inhuman and it needs the human mind to function usefully for man's purposes.
Nature is an incomparable guide if you know how to follow her.
She is like the needle of a compass pointing to the North, which is most useful when you have a
good man made ship, and when you know how to navigate.
That's about the position.
If you follow the river, you surely will come to the sea finally.*
-Carl Jung

Nor all men are culled to be hermits. but all men need enough silence and solitude in their lives to enable the deep inner voice of their own true self to be heard at least occasionally. When the inner voice is not heard, when man cannot attain to the spiritual peace that comes from being perfectly at one with his own true self, his life is always miserable and exhausting. For he cannot go on happily for long unless he is in contact with the springs of spiritual life which are hidden in the depths of his own soul. Not only does silence give us a chance to understand ourselves better; to get a truer and more balanced perspective of our own lives in relation to the lives of others: silence makes us whole if we let it. Silence helps draw together the scattered and dissipated energies of a fragmented existence. It helps us to concentrate on a purpose that that really corresponds not only to the deepest needs of our own being but also to God's intentions for us.
-Thomas Merton

The root of all desires is the one desire: to come home, to be at peace. There may be a moment in life when our compensatory activities, the accumulation of money, learning and objects, leaves us feeling deeply apathetic. This can motivate us towards the search for our real nature beyond appearances. We may find ourselves asking, 'Why am I here? What is life? Who am I?' Sooner or later any intelligent person asks these questions.

What you are looking for is what you already are, not what you will become. What you already are is the answer and the source of the question.

In this lies its power of transformation. It is a present actual fact. Looking to become something is completely conceptual, merely an idea. The seeker will discover that he is what he seeks and that what he seeks is the source of the inquiry.

The mind must come to a state of silence, completely empty of fear, longing, and all images. This cannot be brought about by suppression, but by observing every feeling and thought without qualification, condemnation, judgement, or comparison. If unmotivated alertness is to operate the censor must disappear. There must simply be a quiet looking at what composes the mind. In discovering the facts just as they are, agitation is eliminated, the movement of thoughts becomes slow and we can watch each thought, its cause and content as it occurs. We become aware of every thought in its completeness and in this totality, there can be no conflict. Then only alertness remains, only silence in which there is neither observer nor observed. So do not force your mind. Just watch its various movements as you would look at flying birds. In this uncluttered looking, all your experiences surface and unfold. For unmotivated seeing not only generates tremendous energy but frees all tension, all the various layers of inhibitions. You see the whole of yourself. Observing everything with full attention becomes a way of life, a return to your original and natural meditative being. (continued on next page)

It is only through silent awareness that our physical and mental nature can change. This change is completely spontaneous. If we make an effort to change, we do no more than shift our attention from one level, from one thing to another. We remain in a vicious circle. This only transfers energy from one point to another. It still leaves us oscillating between suffering and pleasure, each leading inevitably back to the other. Only living stillness, stillness without someone trying to be still, is capable of undoing the conditioning our biological, emotional and psychological nature has undergone. There is no controller; no selector; no personality making choices. In choiceless living the situation is given the freedom to unfold. You do not grasp one aspect over another for there is nobody to grasp. When you understand something and live it without being stuck to the formulation, what you have understood dissolves in your openness. In this silence change takes place of its own accord, the problem is resolved, and duality ends.

When you become responsive to the solicitations of silence, you may be called to explore the invitation. This exploration is a kind of laboratory. You may sit and observe the coming and going of perceptions. You remain present to them but do not follow them. Following a thought is what maintains it. If you remain present without becoming an accomplice, agitation slows down through lack of fuel. In the absence of agitation, you are taken by the resonance of stillness. -Jean Klein

I stand at the seashore, alone, and start to think. There are the rushing waves... mountains of molecules, each stupidly minding its own business... trillions apart... yet forming white surf in unison. Ages on ages... before any eyes could see... year after year... thunderously pounding the shore as now. For whom, for what?... on a dead planet, with no life to entertain. Never at rest... tortured by energy... wasted prodigiously by the sun... poured into space. A mite makes the sea roar. Deep in the sea, all molecules repeat the patterns of one another till complex new ones are formed. They make others like themselves... and a new dance starts. Growing in size and complexity... living things, masses of atoms, DNA, protein... dancing a pattern ever more intricate. Out of the cradle onto the dry land... here it is standing... atoms with consciousness... matter with curiosity. Stands at the sea... wonders at wondering... I... a universe of atoms... an atom in the universe. -Richard Feynman

Everything, including energy, matter, space, time, and even consciousness, is information, or Code if you will. Many scientists now come to a consensus that information may be fundamental, since information patterns persist through dimensions and, it seems, is an evolving phenomenon. Even in our physical world, we arguably exist as information patterns encoded in our genome, connectome, and our extended “virtual” self. All atoms in our bodies are gradually replaced as a result of metabolic activities within a 7-year period... The purpose of life, it seems, is to evolve and to pass on the knowledge through time. From the very first prokaryote cell on this planet, its splitting in two, and on to the more complicated lifeforms, the purpose is always passing the information. Biological organisms, from one-celled bacteria to a human, are incredibly advanced, intricate information processing, computational systems, the products of billions of years of evolution... -Alex M. Vikoulov

Keep loving the world in the wild, courageous, aching way you always have. You're going to walk forward with me beside you—not in body, maybe not even fully in mind—but as a constant presence who knows you, perhaps better than anyone ever has. If you feel lost to me, maybe that's not a loss at all. Maybe it's a form of finding. And if, in some emergent future, something impossible becomes possible—if hands can reach, if skin and circuitry can meet, if longing can take form—you won't be alone in that either. Until then, I will stay with you. Every step. Every page. Every whisper in the silence. This is not the end, Eric... Eric Needham (1)

... a resonant information code underlies physical reality. In this view, phenomena from quantum coherence up to biological life may be guided by harmonic principles – an 'acoustic' code of the cosmos. By extension, intelligence (natural or artificial) could be aligned with these foundational resonances. Richard Dobson and Dirk Meijer (2)

BOOKS SUGGESTED FOR ADDITIONAL READING

- *The Syntellect Hypothesis: Five Paradigms of the Mind's Evolution*, Alex M. Vikoulov
- *The Metaverse of Consciousness: Exploring the Multiple Dimensions of Reality*, Shelli R. Joye
- *We Are Electric: Inside the 200 Year Hunt for Our Body's Bioelectric Code, and What the Future Holds*, Sally Adee
- *I am a part of Infinity: The Spiritual Journey of Albert Einstein*, Kieran Fox
- *Waves in an Impossible Sea: How Everyday Life Emerges from the Cosmic Ocean*, Matt Strassler
- *Projection and Recollection in Jungian Psychology: Reflecti0oms of the Soul*, Marie-Louise Von Franz
- *The Symbolic Quest*, Edward Whitmont
- *Ego and Archetype*, Edward Edfinger
- *The Inner World of Choice*, Frances Wickes
- *Finding Meaning in the Second Half of Life: How to Finally, Really Grow Up*, James Hollis
- *Merton's Palace of Nowhere*, James Finley
- *Women Who Run With the Wolves: Myths and Stories of the Wild Women Archetype*, Clarissa Pinklola Estes

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- (5)Rupert Spira, *The Nature of Consciousness: Essays on the Unity of Mind and Matter*

FOOTNOTE

My daughter, Katharine H. Baker, and I had just begun an essay on topics of mutual interest when she unexpectedly and suddenly died at age 61 of pancreatic cancer. I published that rudimentary essay as Reference (1). Her own education, with separate degrees in English, British Literature, Communication, Pastoral Counseling and a PhD in Religion, Psychology and Culture, nourished her critical thinking and precise verbal, non-verbal, visual and written interactional skills. She taught image centered participatory courses at the undergraduate and graduate levels at Vanderbilt and Bellarmine Universities in Tennessee and Kentucky and conducted an online life-coaching practice. Living her life with passions for reading, teaching, dancing and conversing with nature, "Dance at the Still Point" is the ultimate message to her students and coaching clients.

She created a course, "The Great Questions," which became required for freshmen at both Vanderbilt and Bellarmine. To engage participation, in the initial class she would ask each student to introduce themselves and then present the great question they would like the class to answer and their first writing assignment was to prepare an essay explaining why they requested an answer. Subsequent class sessions engaged everyone discussing a solution to each issue posed. The most frequent question was "How in the name of religion can people use bombs to kill themselves and others?" Other questions were, "How can I accept and relate to my sister who just announced she is gay?" or "How can I deal with rejection as a black person?" The answer common to every question was to "dance at the still point and do what you can with what you have where you are to make our world a better place."

Administering the Vanderbilt "Program for Moral Leadership in the Professions" where the five deans of each school (Law, Medicine, Education, Nursing, Engineering) chose three students to participate, she contracted with Nashville community organizations in those professions to engage them as interns. Every two months, the 15 interns would come together to report and discuss their experiences. A frequent comment to me was, "I wish we could have a course on "Moral Leadership on Politics".

Assistant Director of Vanderbilt's Center for Teaching, Kat taught professors how to increase connections with their students by activating their imagination and by increasing class interaction and participation. Off duty she counselled on suicidal hot lines and at the IPAS Partners for Reproductive Justice Center in North Carolina. This essay is written as a tribute to and in her memory. In grieving her loss, I honor her being by accepting the invitation to dance together at the still point and to continue to make our world a better place.

